

EVALUATION OF PARTICLES AND POROSITIES VOLUME FRACTION IN ALUMINUM MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Computed Tomography (CT) has become well established as a nondestructive technique for the inspection, evaluation and analysis tool in the industry. Images generated by CT have to be analyzed in order to reflect density variation in material by x-ray attenuation. In this work, we present the application of this technique for detecting, at mesoscopic scale, defects and variation of volume fraction generated by heterogeneous distribution of particles and porosity in Metal Matrix Composites (MMC). The fabrication technique for these materials was modified in order to produce samples with lot of defects. Tomographic tests were made with a medical scanner GE12000.

KEYWORDS: computed tomography, medical scanner, characterization, non-destructive.

INTRODUCTION

Computed Tomography (CT) is a radiographic method introduced in 1972 for neurological applications but its diagnostic advantages were so dramatic that the technology was quickly extended to industrial applications as well. It has been called one of the ten most significant technical achievements in the last 25 years. CT provides quantitative information on distribution of material density, localization and characterization of defects and dimensional information of the samples [1,2]. It has become well established as an inspection, evaluation and analysis tool in industry. Many of the applications have been in the aerospace and automobile industries, where the high cost and performance requirements of components justify the cost of CT inspection.

Due to several recent advances in industrial CT, especially in terms of data processing methods, the field of this technique is expanding into several new areas. CT possesses several advantages over the others non-destructive (ND) techniques including the ability to extract dimensional data on all external and internal features and no need for special set-ups programming. The images correspond to faithful reconstructions of entire cross-sectional profiles, providing valuable information pertinent to material properties and geometric characteristics of a component.

DESCRIPTION OF THE MATERIAL STUDIED

Special MMC were fabricated for this study made of an A356 aluminum alloy reinforced by large silicone carbide particles. Lot of porosities were also incorporated in order to easily detect their effect on CT measurement. This type of MMC reinforced by large particles can be used for their resistance to abrasion.

The samples were fabricated at the ETS (Ecole de Technologie Supérieure de Montréal) using a modified bottom pouring process. In order to avoid detrimental interfacial reactions between particles and matrix, the silicon content of aluminum matrix has to be increased up to 7%. Because particles oxidation is a real problem in MMC fabrication, a short time for incorporating the particles in the matrix is required. In the process used, a controlled upstream argon flux is added in order to avoid oxidation and generating pores in the matrix. A modified mold permits to obtain a concentration of particles in the bottom part of the specimen.

To create various particles volume fraction, liquid or semi-liquid materials are solidified after sedimentation in different insulating molds. It was therefore possible to produce samples with different concentration of particles and pores.

COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY. TECHNICAL BACKGROUND

The main interest of the tomography is the possibility of visualizing, with a high resolution, a transversal plane of an object without destroying the piece. In the context of non-destructive techniques for the composite materials, this technique has gained importance over the other ND methods such as ultrasound, radiography or Eddy current, that appear to be incomplete or inefficient, for characterizing the inherent defects of this kind of materials. The technical limitation for using a medical scanner for industrial application is that just the materials with low density ($< 3 \text{ gr/cm}^3$) can be analyzed.

CT is based on the measurement of the different absorption coefficient of the sample crossed by an X-ray beam [3]. The CT image represents the point by point linear attenuation coefficients in the slice, which depend on the physical density of the material, its effective atomic number and the X-ray beam energy.

The attenuation in the intensity of a single-energy x-ray beam is defined by the equation of Beer Lambert

$$I = I_0 e^{-\mu L} \quad (1)$$

Where:

I_0 = Incident Intensity

I = Transmitted Intensity

μ = Linear Attenuation Coefficient

L = Thickness of the absorber

Tomographic systems measure the attenuation of intensity from different angles to determine cross-sectional configuration with the aid of a computerized reconstruction. The typical CT scanning system is illustrated in the Fig. 1. The basic experimental device comprises an X-ray source, a collimator, a detector array and a computer system to perform the reconstruction, analysis and data storage media.

Fig. 1: Schematic of computed tomography system [4]

A modified GE 12000 medical scanner was used in these experiments at the French Institute of Petroleum [5]. The tension used for this study was 130 kV with an acquisition time of 3.4 sec. The spatial resolution of this scanner is 200 microns.

The medical systems assign to the air a tomographic density (TD) of -1000 and 0 for the water (Hounsfield scale). Industrial systems often utilize the pixel scale that normally set the value for air at 0 and $+1000$ for the water. This is true only if the same tension is used (120-130 kV). When the energy used is bigger, no standard scaling can be used because the absorption coefficient is a function of the x-ray energy.

For characterizing each sample, 12 tomographic cuts with a 3 mm of thickness were made as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Schematic of the ingot studied showing the tomographic cuts

Information in the reconstructed array of numbers is displayed visually as an image that must be treated in brightness and contrast level in order to have a visual contrast. Color can also be used to enhance the display image where range of CT number is represented as a particular color.

RESULTS

Tomographic Examination

The spatial resolution of the medical scanner ($200\mu\text{m}$) does not allow observing the individual particles. Therefore, the x-ray attenuation is sufficiently sensible to the variation in the concentration of SiC particles. Each color in the tomographic image (Fig. 3) represents a range of local attenuation of x-rays measured in pixel density. In the bottom of the specimen, there is a zone of high attenuation of x-ray. The high attenuation can be attributed to a strong concentration of particles. It was verified by metallography. The upper zone of the CT image (low CT density) represents the aluminum matrix with a low percentage of the reinforcement. These zones of different attenuation of x-rays are clearly observed by the two peaks in the histogram shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 3: CT image of the composite A356/SiCp
Sample 4-3, cut No. 3

Fig. 4: Histogram of pixel density
Sample 4-3, cut No. 3

Quantitative metallographic analysis

In order to compare CT analysis with real material structure, the ingot was physically cut in the same section as for the CT slice using a very thin thread (of 0.5 mm dia.) coated with diamond particles. Samples are polished and then analyzed by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). The analysis is performed on pictures at magnification of X50. Each picture corresponds to real rectangle of 2.5 by 1.7 mm. The software VISILOG was used to compute the average surface fraction of matrix, porosity and particles. The figures 5, 6 and 7 show these results.

Fig. 5: Evolution of Al matrix (%) in the sample 2-3 (cut No. 2)

Fig. 6: Evolution of porosity (%) in the sample 2-3 (cut No. 2)

Fig. 7. Evolution of SiC (%) in the sample 2-3 (cut No. 2)

It is remarked that the concentration of particles at the bottom of the sample (about 25%) was as expected due to the ingot fabrication technique used. The concentration of particles decreases until the center of the transversal cut of the sample, where the percentage of porosity and particles is almost zero. This profile of concentration is presented all the long of the specimen. The SEM images (sample 2-3) shown in the figures 8, 9 and 10 taken respectively at the bottom, in the middle and at the top of the sample show this distribution.

Fig. 8: SEM Image. (Bottom)

Fig. 9: SEM Image (center)

Fig. 10: SEM Image (upper zone)

DISCUSSION

The mechanical properties of MMC are close dependent of the manufacture method used, and therefore, of the defects such as volume fraction of reinforcement, agglomeration or sedimentation of particles, dross and porosities [6,7]. The study of these defects is particularly long and boring by metallography. The x-ray tomography, as is shown in these results, is an efficient way for studying the inherent defects of this new class of materials.

For comparing the tomographic density with the percentage of particles and porosities in the sample it have been used the “surface chart” (Fig. 11). The X and Y axis represent the position in the transversal cut and the colors represent the range of SiC and porosity percentage obtained by metallography (Figures 11a and 11b) or the range of tomographic density (Fig. 11c).

The chart for the tomographic results shows a good similarity with the ones for metallographic studies but it is difficult to separate the effects of porosity and agglomeration of particles. If the matrix remains homogeneous, the variation of tomographic density obtained hold simultaneously the effect of porosity and particles. As it was shown in Fig. 3, the CT density for SiC particles is higher than the aluminum matrix. Therefore, in this case, the influence of porosities is more significant than the one of particles because of the diminution of CT density with respect to the matrix (center of the sample).

Fig. 11: Comparison of results for the composite A356/SiCp (Sample 2-3)

CONCLUSION

Even if the scanner we used was built for medical purposes, it has all the necessary conditions to be used for the non-destructive control of Metal Matrix Composites. The results obtained on the composites studied, show that the CT technique can be used successfully to detect, at mesoscopic scale, the distribution of SiC particles and porosities in the aluminum matrix. Particularly, its reliability, the fast analysis and the possibility of studying all the volume of the sample makes that the utilization of the tomography present incomparable advantages.

It is possible to use computed tomography for controlling MMC fabrication processes and/or parts integrity. Experiments were done on porous aluminum matrix composites reinforced by silicon carbides particles in order to quantify the absorption of x-ray beam.

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